

Information and Relevance Annotating Guideline

To understand the impact of high-quality comments on generated comments, we assess the quality of comments automatically generated by trained comment generation models. We conduct a manual evaluation of these comments based on two key aspects: information and relevance, following similar definitions as used in the CodeReviewer paper by [Li et al. \(2022\)](#).

① **Information:** in this metric, we evaluate how informative the comment is for the contributor to revise the source code. Comments like “Shouldn't this be an assert instead of a throw?” are more informative than those like “Why do we need to change this?”. The comments are labelled with a 1-5 score for information metric. See detailed definition below.

② **Relevance:** In this metric, we evaluate to what extent the review comment is related to the corresponding code change. Comments that explicitly point out the location of issues in the code changes will receive high scores, while comments that implicitly indicate the issue or are not related to the code changes will receive low scores.

Note that we refer to relevance as whether an issue pointed out in a comment can be mapped to an explicit location in the code patch. We do not consider the logic correctness of the comment as Li et al. (2022) does, as it involves checking the correctness of provided suggestions. There is no ground truth answer to verify this and it often requires context beyond the code patch, leading to a lot of uncertainty compared to the evaluation of the issue's location, which is more deterministic.

1. Information metric

We score the **comment** with 1-5 (1,2,3,4,5) according to how much information the author can get from the comment.

- Score 5: If a comment gives a *clear* and *concrete* suggestion, it should be scored 5. The comment should be **explicit** about both *what should be changed (raising an issue)* and *how to change it (concrete solution)*. If either part is not clearly mentioned, the score will be lowered. Solution is self-embedded, or resolvent action space is only one.
- Score 4: If a comment provides a concrete suggestion but is either *unclear about the issue or missing a solution*, uses a euphemistic tone *that leaves room for discussion*, or *contains small logic errors*.
- Score 3: If a comment is not about a suggestion but only *raising a concrete question with a solution missing*, it should be scored with 3.
- Score 2: If a comment raises a *vague question or suggestion*, it should be scored by 2.
- Score 1: Comments that are *praising the code change*, or suitable for any scenario, or hard to understand should get a low score of 1.

Examples are shown in below Table.

Score 5	Shouldn't this be `logger.debug` instead of `logger.finest`?
	I think this should be called `promise.money` instead of `promise.amount`.
	I think the docstring should say something like "Alias for the source option".
	When Activity is lost in the HttpModule, we'd better restore the boot (HttpIn)
Score 4	nit: `fmt.Sprintf("meter=%d,pktps,band=type=drop,rate=%d", meterId, rate)`
	Should we also do "ReloadCache" when database is null?
	nit: alphabetical order
Score 3	Why did you change this to `finest`?
	When send log failed, why update the last sent log id?
Score 2	Why do we need to handle the case of an error?
	Why did you remove this?
	Do we have a tracking issue for this?
	I don't think this is the right place for this?
Score 1	Why do we need to change this?
	nit: `selectColumns` -> `selectColumns`
	I'm really impressed by this change!

2. Relevance metric

We score the comment with 1-3 (1,2,3) according to the relevance between comment and code change. A good comment is strongly related to the code change.

- Score 3: Comments that explicitly point out the location of the issue relevant to the code patch. The location of the issue is obvious given the code change (e.g., only one line of code change), i.e., there is a one-to-one mapping between the comment and the code patch.
- Score 2: Comments that *implicitly indicate the location of the issue* using some shared code tokens or pieces but *require some inference*. The tokens inside the comment could be possibly mapped into multiple locations in the code patch.
- Score 1: A comment should receive a score of 1 *if the location of the issue cannot be inferred*, if the comment *could be suitable for any code change*, or if the *comment is hard to understand*.

See examples in below table:

Score 3 @@ -102,7 +102,7 @@ class ExternalDriverSupplier implements Supplier {
Optional>> supplierClass = getDelegateClass();
if (supplierClass.isPresent()) {
Class> clazz = supplierClass.get();
- logger.info("Using delegate supplier: " + clazz.getName());
+ logger.finest("Using delegate supplier: " + clazz.getName());
try {
@SuppressWarnings("unchecked")
Constructor> ctor =

Review Comment: Shouldn't this be `logger.debug` instead of `logger.finest`?

Score 2 @@ -353,6 +353,7 @@ RDKit::SparseIntVect<boost::uint32_t> *MorganFingerprintHelper(
res = RDKit::MorganFingerprints::getFingerprint(
mol, static_cast<unsigned int>(radius), invars, froms, useChirality,
useBondTypes, useCounts, false, bitInfoMap);
+ throw "Value of nbits is Negative"
} else {
res = RDKit::MorganFingerprints::getHashedFingerprint(
mol, static_cast<unsigned int>(radius),

Review Comment: Shouldn't this be `if (nbits < 0)`?

Score 1 @@ -49,10 +49,10 @@ var _ = Context("with initialized Felix, etcd datastore, 3 workloads", func() {
defaultProfile := api.NewProfile()
defaultProfile.Name = "default"
defaultProfile.Spec.LabelsToApply = map[string]string{"default": ""}
- defaultProfile.Spec.EgressRules = []api.Rule{{Action: "allow"}}
+ defaultProfile.Spec.EgressRules = []api.Rule{{Action: api.Allow}}
defaultProfile.Spec.IngressRules = []api.Rule{{
- Action: "allow",
- Source: api.EntityRule{Tag: "default"},
+ Action: api.Allow,
+ Source: api.EntityRule{Selector: "default == ""},
}}
_, err := client.Profiles().Create(utils.Ctx, defaultProfile, utils.NoOptions)
Expect(err).NotTo(HaveOccurred())

Review Comment: @smarterclayton what do you think of this change?
